

THE LEVEL OF STUDY OF LUTFI'S CREATIVITY**Durdieva Aybolek Xudayberdievna**

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Annotation: Lutfi's lyrical works in his native language have spread to many Turkic-speaking countries besides Khorasan and Movarounnahr. Then the area expanded further. This is evidenced by the manuscripts of the poet's office, which are kept in the libraries of many countries outside the Republic.

Keywords: Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, creative environment, Malik ul-kalami, poet

Alisher Navoi, in his treatise Majlis un-nafois, gives specific information about the poets who wrote in their native language in the 15th century - Atoi, Gadoi, Sakkoki, Amir, Yakin, Muqimi and others. Mawlana Lutfi, on the other hand, said, "Malik ul-kalam of his time had no ministers in Persian and Turkish, but he was more famous in Turkey, and the Turkish devon is also famous, and there are mutaazzir ul-jawb matlas ..." he describes.

Lutfi's great interest in literature from a young age was especially noticeable. The future poet diligently studied Persian and Arabic literature as well as his own Turkic literature. His interest in the legacies of Hafiz, Kamal Khojandi and Nasimi was particularly strong. The literary environment that emerged as a result of the political centralization that took place in Khorasan and Movarounnahr since the time of Amir Temur also attracted Lutfi. His poems became popular and became the subject of literary conversations, which were read on poetry nights. The poems of this poet, who was simply accustomed to the way of life and revered by the dervishes, are characterized by the ability to express deep thoughts in simple words in high artistic colors, and in this respect his poems have attracted the attention of literary patrons such as Navoi and Jamihad gained attention. Only a significant literary legacy has been passed down to us from Mawlana Lutfi, which is one of

his great lyrical works. Alisher Navoi writes about Lutfi's multifaceted lyrical work in *Majolis un-nafois*: It was unique in Turkish and Persian, but it was more famous in Turkey and the Turkish *devon* is famous. Although we do not know that the poet compiled a collection of works in Persian, his contemporaries appreciated his mastery in this language as well.

Epics occupy a special place among Lutfi's literary heritage. One of them is the epic "Flower and Navruz" written in 1411.

Alisher Navoi testifies in *Majlis un-nafois* about Lutfi's epic *Zafarnoma*, which has not survived, and writes: Researchers of Lutfi's work note that the source of the above-mentioned translation of "Zafarnoma" is "Zafarnoma" about the life of Amir Timur, written in Persian by Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi. Thus, Lutfi touched upon a topic of great importance for generations and created a poetic example in Turkish of Ali Yazdi's work, written in the style of history and memory. Professor Ye. E. Bertels suggests that the poet may have planned this *masnavi* as a heroic work in the style of Firdausi's *Shahnameh*. But for some reason the poet did not copy it. Navoi also says that he was "not famous for not copying it into white."

In the sources on the history of oriental culture, it is mentioned that Lutfi also wrote a work on the subject of morality under the name "Mashqun ul-haqayiq". In the work "History of music" by Mulla Ismatullah from Khotan, it is noted that Lutfi was also engaged in the history of music and composed melodies. There is no doubt that the genius poet, who lived for almost a hundred years, also had a wide range of creative work, especially in the field of fiction.

Lutfi's collection of lyrical works in his native language had already spread to many Turkic-speaking countries besides Khorasan and Movarounnahr. Then the area expanded further. This is evidenced by the manuscripts of the poet's office, which are stored in the libraries of many countries outside the Republic. Dozens of rare copies of Lutfi's *devon* are kept in the funds of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, as well as the Institute of Manuscripts.

These sources were comparatively critically studied with the London and Paris copies of the Devon, and a number of the poet's Selected editions were created. In 1987, G. Lutfi's collection "Sensan sevarim", published by the Gulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, is a collection published in the last decade.

Devon includes ghazals, rubais, tuyuqs, qitas, and fards, two of the leading genres of Oriental poetry. It begins, as usual, with poems of praise and praise. In almost all copies of the Devon we see a poem written in the name of Shahrukh Mirzo. In some copies there are poems dedicated to Timurid princes: Boysungur Mirzo, Iskandar Mirzo.

The leading theme of Lutfi's divan is love. This love reflects the external and internal world of man as a mirror. We see in these works that the secular interpretations of love are also reflected in high art. Navoi, in his *Manoqibi Pahlavon Muhammad*, describes Lutfi as a "poet of the apparent people," a poet who excelled in the interpretation of secular subjects. Secular themes, which are more widespread in the poet's lyrics, are at the same time complementing each other, combining them with religious mysticism. In this way they form a unity of metaphor and truth.

The poet's works show that he was influenced by the mystical ideas that were prevalent at that time. God created the world as the embodiment of perfect beauty, discovering the human being's perception of existence, the primacy of love, and his connection with the surrounding community and flora as his most beautiful qualities. But everything in life is temporary, it is in constant motion. Like the seasons of nature, the seasons of human life alternate with each other. Therefore, the hero, who is at the center of Lutfi's ghazals, lives with a sense of enjoyment of all the beauties and blessings of Allah's life.

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